

BMF CP20: Cultural-historical knowledge, social skills, and school events for the young generation in the globalization era

AISDL Team

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1. Project description

1.1. Background

Thanks to the Internet, Information Communication Technology (ICT), and international transportation, the world has become more globalized than ever. In such an era, people are required to obtain high tolerance and inclusiveness levels. For the young generation to survive and thrive, equipping them with a mindset with high tolerance and inclusiveness is essential while they are schooling.

1.2. Main objectives

The current study has two objectives:

1. Examine whether discussions with parents about cultural-historical knowledge and social skills and participation in multicultural school events improve children's and youth's tolerance toward different viewpoints;
2. Examine whether discussions with parents about cultural-historical knowledge and social skills and participation in multicultural school events improve children's and youth's general inclusiveness.

1.3. Materials

The mindsponge theory will be used for conceptual development, and Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF) analytics will be used for statistical analysis on a dataset of 2069 students in Vietnamese primary, secondary, and high schools [1-3]. The bayesvl R package, aided by the Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm, will be employed for statistical analyses [4]. All the materials and code for this study will be made available only to reduce the cost of doing science and transparency. For more information on BMF analytics, portal users can refer to the following book [5].

1.4. Main findings

The findings show that discussions with parents about cultural-historical knowledge and social skills and participation in multicultural school events can improve students' tolerance toward different viewpoints (see Figure 1). However, the effect of discussions with parents about cultural-historical knowledge of other countries is only moderately reliable. Meanwhile, discussions with parents about cultural-historical knowledge and social skills can improve children's and youth's general inclusiveness, but participation in multicultural school events does not (see Figure 2).

Figure 1. Posterior distributions of the first analytical model's coefficients.

Figure 2. Posterior distributions of the second analytical model's coefficients

2. Collaboration procedure

Portal users should follow these steps to register to participate in this research project:

- Create an account on the website (preferably using an institution's email).
- Comment your name, affiliation, and your desired role (e.g., literature review, method and material description, result presentation, discussion, etc.) in the project below this post.
- Patiently wait for the formal agreement on the project from the AISDL mentor.

If you have further inquiries, please contact us at aisdl_team@mindsponge.info.

If you have been invited to join the project by an AISDL member, you are still encouraged to follow the above formal steps.

All the resources for conducting and writing the research manuscript will be distributed upon project participation.

AISDL mentor for this project: **Minh-Phuong Thi Duong**.

AISDL members who have joined this project: Minh-Hoang Nguyen, and Quan-Hoang Vuong.

The research project strictly adheres to scientific integrity standards, including authorship rights and obligations. We look forward to working with participants on this research project.

**Remarks: Dr. Minh-Phuong Thi Duong (Ton Duc Thang University) has taken over the responsibilities to coordinate and mentor this project, effective from August 30, 2024. [Last updated: Sept. 1, 2024]*

References

[1] Nguyen MH, La VP, Le TT, Vuong QH. (2022). [Introduction to Bayesian Mindsponge Framework analytics: An innovative method for social and psychological research](#). *MethodsX*, 9, 101808.

[2] Nguyen HL, et al. (2021). [School students' perception, attitudes and skills regarding global citizenship-dataset from Vietnam](#). *Data in Brief*, 37, 107162.

[3] Vuong QH. (2023). [Mindsponge Theory](#). De Gruyter.

[4] La VP, Vuong QH. (2019). [bayesvl: Visually Learning the Graphical Structure of Bayesian Networks and Performing MCMC with 'Stan'](#). *The Comprehensive R Archive Network*.

[5] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH, La VP. (2022). [The mindsponge and BMF analytics for innovative thinking in social sciences and humanities](#). De Gruyter.

